

The Co-Design of building deep retrofitting in distressed urban areas: lessons from e-SAFE

Laura Saija* (corresponding author) laura.saija@unict.it

Giulia Li Destri Nicosia*

Venera Pavone*

* *Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture, University of Catania, Italy*

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Abstract

This article addresses the realm of co-design in building deep retrofitting in distressed urban areas. Drawing from a pilot experience conducted between 2020 and 2023 in Catania, Italy, as part of the Horizon 2020 project e-SAFE, the authors discuss the scholarly relevance of the lessons learned through a process of engagement of public housing residents in the co-design of their building's retrofitting. Drawing from both socio-technical and urban planning literature, the paper conceptualizes co-design as a process that should provide spaces for shared learning and creativity, on the one side, and negotiability between residents and experts, on the other. In the Catania experience, co-design has encountered several obstacles, especially due to strings attached to the funded grant as well as the unfortunate socio-political conjuncture. While these obstacles made hard to keep spaces of shared creativity open, it was crucial to at least provide spaces for negotiation, especially over those technological choices having a direct impact on residents' relational economics. In general, the paper argues the importance of distinguishing between these two dimensions ensuring flexibility, so that even if shared creativity is constrained by circumstances, negotiable spaces can still be provided.

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Introduction

In the light of climate change and global governmental commitments toward energy savings and decarbonization goals, experts in building retrofitting are increasingly focusing on deep retrofitting, i.e. the significant enhancement of overall energy performance and, in seismic prone regions, structural resilience. Within this discourse, co-design emerges as a pivotal strategy for achieving successful deep retrofitting, especially in the socio-technical literature which views buildings as complex systems where materials, technology, and humans constantly interact and influence each other.

This recent technology-driven focus on co-design is interestingly converging with a more politicized debate on codesign – ongoing since the 1960s – that sees both urban scholars and building designers pushing experts to work not *for* people but *with* people, as a strategy for empowering the most distressed urban residents and making urban decision-making more equitable.

This article draws from both socio-technological and urban planning literature, seeking to contribute to the debate on the feasibility and the significance of co-design in deep retrofitting with a specific focus on distressed urban areas. Given that existing deteriorated buildings are predominantly situated in such neighbourhoods, it is worth wondering whether co-design hold particular relevance and/or encounter specific challenges in these types of areas. This paper addresses this question, drawing from a co-design experience conducted between 2020 and 2023 in the City of Catania (Sicily, Italy), involving the renovation of a public housing building.

2. Co-design in building deep retrofitting, combining the socio-technical literature with an urban planning perspective

The heightened global awareness of humanity's irreversible impact on Earth's ecological systems has led scholars to reframe the discourse on retrofitting in the building sector. The conventional emphasis on 'human comfort' has been overshadowed by a concentrated focus on the decarbonization of the existing building stock. This shift is particularly salient in Europe, where existing buildings are estimated to be accountable for 40% of energy consumption and 36% of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions.

In pursuit of more ambitious energy-saving strategies, scholars have progressively employed the term 'deep retrofitting' to denote a series of comprehensive upgrades aimed at significantly reducing both the delivered and final energy consumption of a building compared to pre-renovation levels, ultimately resulting in a very high energy performance (Directive 2012/27/EU). Notably, in seismic-prone regions, deep retrofitting encompasses structural enhancements since many existing buildings fail to meet contemporary building codes, potentially undermining the efficacy of energy-focused refurbishment efforts (Belleri & Marini 2016, Margani et al. 2020).

The prominence of 'deep retrofitting' in the scholarly debate has changed the way scholars understand the role of buildings-users in the design process, paving the way for co-design to acquire a central role.

Co-design has often been considered as an important strategy to approach building retrofitting – particularly when addressing vulnerable end-users such as low-income elderly individuals (Hadjiri et al., 2023), school students (Ghaziani, 2008), or hospital users (Reay et al., 2017) –. However, the socio-technical perspective corresponds to an increase of its importance.

The socio-technical literature conceptualizes buildings as complex systems in which physical components (e.g. heating/cooling systems) are interdependent with social variables, namely residents' behaviors (Klein, 2014). When this perspective is applied to deep retrofitting, which entails the restructuring of the whole system, it requires residents' learning how to properly relate with the new technologies (Janda & Killip 2013, Baborska-Narożny & Stevenson 2019), overcoming significant cognitive barriers that may impede upgrades (Hoffman & Henn 2008, Klöckner & Nayum 2017, Caballero & Della Valle 2021). The importance of residents' learning increases together with the level of technological innovation (Pretlove & Kade 2016). In the most advanced conceptualizations of buildings as socio-technical systems, influenced by complexity theory and contemporary social theories on the bidirectionality of the humans-environment relationship (Cole et al. 2008, Lowe et al. 2018), design scholars have begun to look at 'building-users' as 'inhabitants' whose behaviours are intertwined with their rationality and creativity (Sanders & Stappers 2008). This aligns with what Sanders & Stappers' (2008) depict as a trend in all design sectors, i.e., an increasing recognition of the necessity to transcend user-centred design approaches – wherein users act as passive data sources, interviewed by experts, executing instructed tasks, and/or providing opinions on ideas already generated by others – towards genuine processes of co-creation. In such processes, users actively engage in the design phase, collaborate equally with experts, and contribute to the creative process. This perspective encourages buildings' scholars to advocate for a broader participatory approach among all stakeholders involved in a retrofitting endeavour, including developers (Boess et al., 2018).

While this viewpoint represents a major theoretical advancement, supported by new research methods – especially case-study methods – that help scholars “account not only for the technical but also the social, and interactions between them” (Lowe et al. 2017, p.3), the widespread adoption of co-design in the building retrofitting sector is still lagging behind scholars' expectations.

The challenges inherent in co-design and deep retrofitting can be effectively reconsidered by drawing from the urban planning literature. Urban planners regularly confront the reality that many buildings requiring deep renovation are situated in distressed neighbourhoods (Paris & Bianchi, 2016; Monteiro et al., 2017), characterized by elevated levels of not only physical deterioration but also socio-economic hardship. These encompass aging low-income and public housing areas as well as declining middle-class neighbourhoods (Haase et al 2016). In such areas, retrofitting initiatives, particularly deep retrofitting, faces mostly non-technological challenges. For instance, low-income property owners may lack the economic means to undertake retrofitting endeavours, while absentee landlords may lack the motivation (Norgaard, 2009; Olazabal and Pascual, 2015). Furthermore, retrofitting efforts, when undertaken, might yield adverse outcomes for occupants, such as increased debt among low-income groups, rental increases, and gentrification (Baeten et. al, 2017; Bouzarovski et al., 2018; Grossmann 2019; del Pulgar, 2021; Sander and Weissermel, 2023), even in the context of regeneration projects involving public housing (Goetz 2003).

Within these contexts, numerous planning scholars argue the importance of engaging distressed residents not as passive users but as political actors. This perspective adds an ethical and political dimension to the socio-technical framework. Since Arnstein's seminal article in 1969, planning scholars have highlighted the importance of effectively sharing decision-making power with residents inhabiting distressed urban areas as a primary strategy to mitigate both

enduring distress stemming from disinvestment and decay (see Heskin, 1991, among others), and additional distress resulting from the escalation of real estate values driven by technological and financial innovations (Madden and Marcuse, 2016). In a similar vein, several urban studies highlight the political and economic barriers hindering the meaningful involvement of distressed residents in decision-making processes. Mouffe's inspired urban scholars have studied the instrumental use of participatory methods to asphyxiate social conflict in the contemporary post-political era (Wilson and Swyngedouw, 2014), for the benefit of those who view buildings merely as financial assets and real estates, contrasting with those who perceive buildings as lived, social spaces (Madden and Marcuse, 2016). Such a perspective has stimulated a re-politicization of the scholarly debate on the role of residents in urban planning and design (Wilson and Swyngedouw, 2014; Huybrechts et al, 2017).

Overall, comparing co-design conceptualizations developed within these two streams of literature, one can notice that:

- The adoption of a socio-technical perspective on buildings' retrofitting leads to a co-design approach focused on shared learning and creativity, with an emphasis on ways in which 'inhabitants' can learn about contemporary environmental challenges and new technological opportunities so that they can creatively contribute to design choices;
- The adoption of an urban planning perspective for the betterment of distressed urban areas leads to a co-design approach focused on shared decision-making, i.e., the importance of having spaces of negotiability where 'inhabitants' can have a say – even through conflict – over design aspects and features that significantly impact their life.

Drawing from both socio-technical and urban planning literature, we adopt a conceptualization of co-design as a process for designing building retrofits that encompasses both spaces of shared learning and creativity – where the emphasis is on residents' engagement with novelties – as well as spaces of negotiability – where the emphasis is on residents' engagement with power dynamics –.

Ideally, learning, creativity, and negotiability should intersect at every stage of the co-design process. However, we argue for the importance of distinguishing between these dimensions to ensure flexibility. Our own experience in Catania has shown that, even if the first dimension is constrained by circumstances, preserving openness in the second remains crucial.

3. Methodology & Background

In response to the growing interest in deriving insights from real-world retrofitting endeavours (Lowe et. al. 2018, Boess 2018), our study focuses on a singular case of deep retrofitting co-design within a distressed urban area.

Methodologically, our case was developed using Participatory Action-Research (PAR), a label referring to “a global family of related approaches that integrate theory and action with the goal of addressing important organizational, community and social issues together with those who experience them” (Coghlan & Brydon-Miller 2014, p. XXV). PAR has emerged in the 70s from a variety of applied research areas, thanks to scholars working on the democratization of development in colonial contexts like South America (Bonilla et al 1972) or Africa (Hall 1972, Chambers 1986) and others interested in enhancing sociology's social relevance (Whyte 1982). It is based on the idea that the direct collaboration between researchers and individuals with a vested interest in the research outcomes can simultaneously generate change *and* scientifically relevant knowledge. This knowledge often emerges through a cyclical process of trial and error, wherein researchers learn lessons confronting both successes and failures (Greenwood & Levin 1998) and share them in writing through first-person narratives (Saija 2014).

In the subsequent sections, we share our PAR experience, where our work as researchers – in collaboration with a group of public housing residents – was aimed at the deep retrofitting of their deteriorated building. We delineate the lessons learned from our endeavour to effectively engage in the co-design process, reflecting on both successful strategies and areas where challenges persisted, focusing on what we think is of interest for the scholarly codesign community.

Our PAR process occurred between 2020 and 2023, within the framework of a Horizon 2020 project called “e-SAFE - Energy and Seismic Affordable rEnovation solutions” submitted by a research consortium coordinated by the University of Catania. The project was submitted to a call titled: “Decarbonisation of the EU building stock: innovative approaches and affordable solutions changing the market for buildings renovation.” The call specifically asked for proposals aimed at overcoming current non-technological challenges faced by deep-retrofitting, such as the financial and socio-economic ones. The primary objective of the e-SAFE project was to pioneer a novel retrofitting technology utilizing wood-based prefabricated panels. These panels were designed to enhance both energy efficiency and seismic resilience by being affixed externally to existing Reinforced Concrete (RC) structures via innovative joints engineered to dissipate seismic energy during earthquakes (Evola et al., 2021). A pivotal component of the e-SAFE project involved testing the feasibility of these new technologies in distressed urban areas, characterized by pronounced financial and socio-economic impediments.

The e-SAFE project, among its various endeavours, provided funding for the deep renovation of a single pilot building located in Catania, Eastern Sicily. This initiative engaged designers with diverse areas of expertise, encompassing structural engineering, architecture, building construction, thermal systems engineering, and urban planning. The project set an expectation to employ a co-design approach throughout the process.

The authors’ role primarily focused on facilitating residents’ engagement, designing the process, and orchestrating events and activities involving both residents and experts. Notably, some of these experts had limited or no prior experience with co-design methodologies.

4. Context

Catania, the second-largest city in Southern Italy’s Sicily region, is facing widespread socio-economic challenges, creating a context of significant distress.

In 2020, it exhibited the lowest average household income among Italian cities with over 150,000 residents, standing at €6,889, nearly half the national average (source: ISEE Report 2020). Moreover, it reported an unusually high percentage of residents receiving welfare benefits, reaching 12% in 2019, surpassing the regional average by 4 percentage points—already the second highest in the nation (data from the Ministry of Labor’s Income Support Monitoring).

In 2021, we conducted 42 interviews with local stakeholders somehow connected to the retrofitting sector (building design professionals, public officials, developers, as well as representatives of banks, insurances, tenants’ unions, grassroots organizations, and social service providers). They unanimously agreed on the necessity of adopting an urban planning perspective to address the obstacles hindering deep retrofitting efforts. As one developer stated, “there are neighbourhoods where no-one would even think about doing it [deep retrofitting], even if we offer to work for free.” Stakeholders with experience in distressed neighbourhoods argued the importance of viewing building retrofitting not only as an end but also as a means to tackle other pressing socio-economic issues.

In the context of an already challenging urban environment, the selected pilot area, the Acquicella Public Housing complex, faces heightened distress. The complex was built by the local Public Housing Authority (IACP Catania, IACP from now on) in the 1960s inside an area originally designated for manufacturing (Figure 1), which is the reason of its distance from residential services and amenities. Today, most of these productive facilities are vacant and the overall area is declining. The area's real estate value reflects its blighted condition, with the average price per square meter of floor area standing at €600, which is only half of Catania's already modest average of €1200 per square meter (source: Italian Revenue Agency website).

Figure 1. Current Land Use of the Acquicella Porto industrial district (elaborated by the authors on official city cartography)

Among the ten blocks comprising the Acquicella complex, all afflicted by severe deterioration stemming from both substandard construction and long-term neglect, the chosen building for retrofitting was the five-story structure identified as block H. Each floor of Block H accommodates two housing units, with IACP owning 70% of the units within the building. As outlined in the findings of the e-SAFE research team (D'Urso et al. 2022), Block H exhibits several critical issues, such as significant heat losses resulting from the lack of thermal insulation; high energy consumption rates associated with inefficient appliances like electric boilers and outdated split units; a low-quality Reinforced Concrete (RC) structure characterized by a reduced quantity of steel bars (8mm) and unsuitable concrete composition; deteriorated finishes; widespread mould and moisture.

The analysis of qualitative data collected in 2021 through interviews with at least one representative from each one of the 10 households within the building, revealed that:

- The building housed: 4 families of 4 to 6 members, with two of these families including people with disabilities and minors, 2 one-person households (elderly residents), and four families with 2-3 members, including minors, totalling 28 people. 7 of the 10 housing units were IACP rentals while the remaining 3 flats were owner-occupied.
- Residents regarded IACP as an absentee landlord. Over 60 years, the only repairs undertaken on the building were carried out not by the IACP but by residents, and these consisted of sporadic, minor, non-structural fixes. Consequently, some tenants of IACP-owned units justified non-payment of rent due to this perceived neglect.
- Relationships amongst residents exhibited a dual nature. On the one hand, there were instances of solidarity and collaboration, such as mutual childcare and meal-sharing. On the other hand, there was notable conflict for the use of communal spaces, such as the roof terrace and the courtyard, alongside a lack of mutual accountability over common expenses.

4. From co-analysis to preliminary co-design (phase I)

Residents' engagement in e-SAFE officially began in July 2020. As a first step, researchers' have spent a couple of afternoons visiting each apartment, engaging in face-to-face conversations and distributing flyers. As a consequence, at least one representative from each household participated in an informative meeting held on July 23rd under the sparse trees in the courtyard of Block H. After being informed about the availability of EU funding for deep renovation contingent upon their participation in co-design activities, residents looked initially very sceptical, recounting instances of institutional neglect and mismanagement (lack of maintenance, flooding, broken sewers, inadequate trash collection services, etc.). They also mentioned all the broken promises made by local politicians periodically fishing for votes. Despite their scepticism, residents recognized the opportunity for much needed improvements to a building they described as "almost falling over people's heads". They particularly appreciated the fact that the e-SAFE technology did not require their relocation during the retrofitting process.

As a result, an average of 60% of households have participated in most activities throughout the more-than two-year-long process (Figure 2).

When & where	what	Who's involved	Tools and activities
Jul 2020 bldg. H courtyard	first 'informative' meeting	IACP representatives, residents, Unict researchers	Informal, unstructured conversation
<i>Oct 2020 – e-SAFE official start date</i>			
Nov-Dec 2020 (via phone)	Residents' survey	Authors, residents	Structured survey of building H occupants
Sept-Oct 2021 bldg. H courtyard	Co-design workshop	Unict researchers, design students, residents, IACP representatives)	Informative seminars, demonstrations with maquettes, photovoice, expert-led apartments' survey
Mar-Apr 2022 bldg. H courtyard	2 thematic meetings on Verandas and <i>Superbonus</i>	Unict researchers, IACP representative and residents	Experts' presentations followed by residents' feedback
Jul 2022 bldg. H courtyard	Meeting on structural choices	Unict researchers, IACP representative and residents	Experts' presentations followed by residents' feedback
Dec 2022 bldg. H courtyard	Final thematic meeting on thermal plants	Unict researchers, IACP representative and residents	Experts' presentations followed by residents' feedback

Figure 2 Timeline and overview of the co-design activities.

Co-design began with an intensive workshop spanning from September 17th to October 16th, 2021, involving residents, researchers in structural engineering, architecture, building construction, and thermal systems engineering, as well as 20 building design students. Except for a couple of studio activities reserved to researchers and students, activities were all scheduled during weekends and located in the pilot courtyard in order to facilitate residents' participation.

The workshop kicked off with the formalization of mutual commitments amongst participants: residents pledged to participate in scheduled co-design activities, while experts committed to attentive listening, minimizing disturbance to agreed-upon dates, and ensuring transparency in decision-making. A large portion of the discussion centred on money, considered a 'foundational' space of negotiability. As one resident put it, it was crucial to agree on "what we can afford and how." Residents were informed that the e-SAFE project allocated €487.000 + 10% VAT for specific items, yet certain necessary interventions were not covered by the project (refer to table 1 for specifics). IACP officials and the three homeowners agreed to contribute their share (nearly €6000 for each homeowner and €42.000 for IACP) to cover all the necessary expenses.

Table 1. List of the types of retrofit works needed for the block H

	<i>Covered by e-SAFE</i>	<i>Not covered</i>
New structural and insulated e-SAFE panels on the façade	X	
Staircase and balconies' consolidation and replastering		X
Photovoltaic panels	X	
New HVAC system	X	
New Domestic Hot Water system	X	
Seismic reinforcement	X	
New windows and shutters for housing units	X	
Roof insulation and waterproofing	X	
New entrance door and staircase windows		X
Veranda dismantling & replacement		X
Painting of balconies' parapets and external fences		X

Figure 3. Students using wooden maquettes to discuss with residents how e-SAFE panel will enhance block H's seismic preparedness, during the sept-oct 2021 co-design workshop (ph by L. Saija).

The workshop proceeded with a **co-analysis** phase aimed to foster residents' learning and to facilitate experts' data collection. Another important aim was raising awareness among experts – particularly those lacking prior co-design experience – regarding potential areas for shared creativity and negotiation. In particular:

- **Structural engineers** instructed students to construct a wooden maquette of the building, demonstrating where e-SAFE structural elements (prefabricated anti-seismic panels) would be attached. Students simulated the effect of the e-SAFE panels during an earthquake, shaking the maquette with and without the e-SAFE panels (simulated with small balsa pieces glued to the structure), showcasing to residents the increased

structural resilience thanks to the panels (Figure 3). This activity succeeded in stimulating both students' and residents' learning about seismic vulnerability and preparedness (which was not one of residents' concerns beforehand). However, experts failed to identify spaces for shared creativity or negotiability.

- **Thermal systems' engineers** held an informative session with residents on the planned retrofitting measures relevant to thermal comfort and savings. These measures were windows replacement, a new domestic water heating system, and a new centralized heating/cooling system powered by photovoltaic roof panels. The session provided no space for shared creativity and limited space for negotiability. Negotiation opportunities were confined to determining the precise locations inside apartments and in the courtyard of pre-determined equipment, as well as a choice between two predefined fan-coils options.
- **Architects and architectural engineers** engaged residents in an exercise focused on functional and aesthetics aspects. Residents were shown a second maquette reproducing their building' appearance, that was used as a base for a discussion on its aesthetics. The discussion ended with residents agreeing on the fact that retrofitting was a good occasion to enhance the 'beauty' of their building. Experts were optimistic about the possibility to have plenty of space for learning, shared creativity and negotiability of aesthetic and functional aspects in the upcoming co-design phase.

In synthesis, only architects were able to plan for further activities implying spaces for shared creativity, while the other experts were only able to identify limited spaces for negotiation.

Overall, these co-analysis seminars persuaded 100% of the residents to grant engineers and students access to their homes for technical surveys on internal distributions, heating and cooling systems, as well as water and energy consumption habits. Surveys revealed unauthorized modifications to most units, including kitchen installations on balconies and "verandas" (windows enclosing balconies; Figure 4).

Figure 4. Bloch H façade before (left) and after (right) the removal of verandas (ph. by L. Saija).

Following co-analysis, the workshop transitioned to the stage of co-design – even if only on aesthetic and functional aspects of the design –, operating under the assumption that residents’ exposure to technical knowledge had prepared them for engaging in the creative part of the process.

Co-design began with architects launching a photovoice activity, i.e., a participatory technique utilizing participants-generated photos to facilitate communication on a topic among individuals who may not possess specialized expertise in that area (Carpenter 2002). Each resident was tasked with sharing at least one picture of their “dream building”, i.e., an image independently sourced from the web or captured within the city, depicting a building resembling to theirs but with a much ‘nicer’ appearance. These photos were subsequently projected and collectively discussed to determine “shared (and feasible) aesthetic options”.

Building upon these options, students’ teams produced six alternative design solutions, which were then presented to residents in the form of digital 3D models as well as printed maquette covers glued to the maquette reproducing the building’s current aesthetic appearance. All design proposals incorporated lightweight, corrosion-resistant, and humidity-resistant materials, along with attributes such as easy maintenance, high energy and acoustic performance, durability, fire resistance, and a range of aesthetic finishes. Finally, residents voted on their top three preferred solutions and offered additional suggestions on how to blend elements from multiple options to further enhance the design.

The workshop ended with a co-created preliminary design, anticipating it to serve as the groundwork for the detailed design phase. Additionally, residents agreed to voluntarily dismantle their outdoor kitchens and verandas, albeit reluctantly, understanding that this action was a prerequisite for obtaining the retrofitting permit from local authorities.

This preliminary design phase, aimed at establishing spaces of learning, creativity and negotiability, demonstrated notable disparities in co-design possibilities across different areas of expertise. While residents’ learning on the meaning and the functioning of the basic technological choices occurred almost equally in each area, not the same can be said about shared creativity and negotiability. Aesthetics and functional aspects were fully open to shared creativity and negotiation. On the contrary, only some negotiation occurred about thermal plants while almost no negotiation occurred in the realm of structural choices.

5. Detailed co-design facing external challenges (phase II)

The detailed design phase commenced with the intention of involving residents in small creative and decision-making steps throughout the process via occasional thematic meetings. The intention was to keep spaces of, at least, negotiability as open as possible. Unfortunately, between March and December 2022, the process was greatly influenced by external factors.

During the work in Catania, the overall European retrofitting sector was facing challenges due to the war in Ukraine, which disrupted the import of several construction materials, resulting in price increases (Toygar & Yildirim 2023). Such a trend was being exacerbated, in Italy, by the launch in July 2020 of a national policy called *Superbonus*. Under this policy, building owners had the opportunity to apply for fiscal incentives covering 110% of retrofitting costs, which led to a surge in retrofitting activities and heightened demand for construction materials and components. Consequently, a reassessment of the “bill of

quantities” for the renovation of block H revealed a significant escalation in the initial estimated retrofitting budget from €487.000 to €1,5 million by February 2022.

A first thematic co-design meeting was convened on March 18th, 2022, primarily to discuss with residents that the removal of their unauthorized verandas was a legal precondition for applying for a retrofitting permit with local authorities. Additionally, the meeting aimed to tackle the pressing budgetary issue. Residents were apprised of the option to apply for the *Superbonus*. The transferability of *Superbonus* financial credits to third parties allowed hiring a contractor interested in: acquiring Block H’s owners’ *Superbonus* fiscal credits to be used to leverage bank credit while assuming all practical, legal and financial responsibilities for the execution of the retrofitting works. This intricate financial arrangement was explained to residents. Despite the increased complexity and potential delays in the project timeline, residents recognized this approach as the sole viable path forward for what had become a very expensive retrofitting endeavour, since governmental incentives would have reduced their co-pays to about €1.500 per household, compared to the previous €6.000. The meeting ended with residents unanimously agreeing to proceed with the *Superbonus* option and, also, to remove all verandas by the end of the first week of April (Figure 4).

While the process of hiring a contractor was underway, two other meetings took place. On April 20th, 2022, experts and residents finalized their preferences on façade’s materials and colours as well as on how to integrate sun-shading in the panels (Figure 5). On July 20th, 2022, at the structural engineers’ suggestion, residents also agreed to reduce the size of one of their windows to enhance the structural integrity of the new e-SAFE cover.

Figure 5. A rendering of the preliminary design for the retrofitting of the Building H (image: e-SAFE research team archive).

A final and notably contentious co-design meeting was convened on December 20th, 2022, to address a significant issue that had surfaced during prior discussions. During the previous meetings, residents had repeatedly expressed concerns about their understanding of, and apprehensions regarding, the installation of the new centralized HVAC system. Specifically, they had voiced worries about potential disruptions during installation and disapproval of new wiring and piping on interior walls. For this reason, for the December meeting, HVAC

engineers were tasked with providing residents with a straightforward explanation of the benefits and drawbacks of the new system, particularly in terms of savings and thermal comfort. Experts outlined that the new HVAC system would complement the existing system powering appliances. Based on previously collected data on residents' bills, experts presented a rough estimate of an anticipated energy bill reduction exceeding 50%, a fact expected to be received positively by residents.

Residents' reactions were unexpectedly negative. For those with very limited incomes, the prospect of savings held little significance as they could not afford to utilize cooling systems in the first place (in one resident's words "I cannot afford AC, and I don't need it, so I don't want it"). Additionally, residents were averse to the idea of maintaining two separate systems, each potentially resulting in separate monthly bills, which implied a duplication of fixed costs. As expressed by another resident, "there is no way I am going to pay taxes, twice." In other words, they did not welcome the duplication of a 'contractual relationship' with an entity (the energy provider) perceived as 'the enemy.' Furthermore, the concept of a centralized system, despite its efficiency and cost-saving potential, was met with resistance. Residents expressed concerns about shared fixed costs, fearing that the financial strain of a single household could jeopardize service for all residents in the building. As another resident explained, "we cannot really deal with a centralized system, with shared fixed costs, in a place where we have troubles collecting a few euros, every month, to pay the cleaning of the communal staircase." Ultimately, the meeting concluded with a shared commitment to continue the controversial debate, but the matter was soon outshined by a much bigger problem: the failure of the *Superbonus* procedure.

Since January 2023, IACP and e-SAFE researchers had carried out several efforts to secure a contractor for the project, but they had all proven unsuccessful due to contractors' inability to access bank credits or their being busy with more 'convenient' contracts (retrofitting with richer clients willing to pay cash for extra works). Therefore, the Block H procedure was still pending when, in June 2023, the government officially ceased the transfer of fiscal credits following the official evaluation by the Italian Fiscal Court of the *Superbonus* as a financial bubble that had disproportionately benefited the wealthiest (Corte dei Conti, 2023). IACP representatives had intermittently updated residents, who were increasingly disheartened by the ongoing delays. Ultimately, a final decision was reached in a series of meeting amongst Building H's owners convened between June 2023 and February 2024: to proceed even in the absence of the fiscal incentives and in the face of significant price increases, with a significantly downsized project. The scope of work to be undertaken with the unaltered e-SAFE budget of €487,000 + 10% VAT focused solely on insulating external panels for the façade and installing photovoltaic panels to power a new system for domestic hot water production and lighting for the common staircase. Enhancements to seismic resistance, new windows for housing units, and the HVAC system were no longer included in the project scope. Both IACP and homeowners decided to cover an increase of their co-pay equal to respectively €11800 €6400 each.

According to a round of final interviews, residents had mixed feelings about the project. For months, waiting for the *Superbonus* procedure to be completed, one resident interpreted the general feeling of frustration: "we told you, this was, again, another promise destined to remain unfulfilled". Therefore, by the end of the project, even though they were all disappointed about the downsizing and the increase of prices, the actual approval of the final budget and the beginning of the construction works (Spring 2024) was perceived as better outcome than the complete failure they had anticipated.

6. Concluding remarks

Does building deep retrofitting co-design in particularly distressed urban areas face specific obstacles and /or acquire particular significance? Such a question was the basis of the 2-year-long Acquicella co-design experience, whose evolution, along different phases, provide insights that might be of general interest.

Overall, the Acquicella neighbourhood can be considered representative of what urban planners might define a distressed urban area, where buildings' long-term physical decay comes together with residents' socio-economic distress. Here, it is interesting to notice that the most significant obstacles faced by deep retrofitting were not related to the level of urban distress or other context-based aspects, but rather to contingent external factors.

The main obstacles derived from global conflicts and the national *Superbonus* policy negatively impacting the market and, therefore, the financial feasibility of a low-cost retrofitting endeavour, regardless the effective use of co-design. Other obstacles were related to the scarcity of spaces for shared creativity and negotiability in the main areas of retrofitting expertise required by e-SAFE, i.e., structural engineering and thermal systems' engineering. Despite the fact that the socio-technical literature postulates an increase in residents' engagement proportional to the level of technological innovation (Janda and Killip 2013, Baborska-Narožny and Stevenson 2019, Pretlove and Kade 2016), in our experience it has been the exact opposite. This was attributable not to a lack of experts' willingness but rather to the fact that the most important part of structural and energy-related decision-making had been concluded way before co-design, during the grant writing phase. In other words, the fact that building H was to be retrofitted to test new predefined specific technologies prevented residents from questioning basic technological choices, such as the centralized nature of the new plant system.

Overall, initial expectations – specifically, the deep retrofitting of the Acquicella building through a design co-created by both experts and residents – did not align with the actual outcomes, which involved only partial retrofitting based on a design where residents contributed solely to the aesthetic and functional aspects, not the technological and structural ones. However, there is more to be said about the significance of co-design in distressed urban areas. In our experience, co-design was instrumental to the partial success of the project. Building H is finally going to be retrofitted. No 'deeply', but surely 'balconies will stop falling over our heads' (in one of the residents' words).

Throughout 2022 and 2023, low-income residents with a history of neglect by local institutions, despite their skepticism and mistrust, have participated in all the scheduled codesign activities, have voluntarily removed their outdoor kitchens and verandas, have endured delays and disappointments, and even accepted a disappointing conclusion (increased co-pays for partial retrofitting). We believe this was possible thanks to the fact that, even when shared creativity was not allowed, residents were able to join spaces of negotiation, where to express hanger and frustration as well as, most importantly, partaking important financial and technological decisions. In particular, amongst the items to be excluded from the final reduced budget, they succeeded to eliminate the problematic centralized system while keeping money for better insulation.

In addition to this, codesign has revealed the incompleteness of experts' perception of e-SAFE's suitability for buildings in distressed urban areas. During the development of the e-

SAFE proposal, the idea was that e-SAFE was good for low-income areas and public housing based on two assumptions: (1) the possibility of limiting works to the outside of the building avoiding residents' relocation and (2) significant savings to individual households' energy bills.

This first assumption has been only partially confirmed by our experience. During the first meeting with residents', in 2020, the idea that retrofitting did not require relocation was highly welcomed. However, after their learning about buildings' vulnerability to earthquakes, all residents welcomed major disturbances (like the reduction of a window to enhance structural soundness) to the extent that there are reasons to believe that even an eventual necessary temporary relocation might be accepted if considered necessary.

The second assumption was proved false in the Acquicella case, as evidenced by residents' negative reactions to the new 'efficient' HVAC system, whose centralized nature was in contrast with the lack of mutual financial accountability amongst low-income households.

Overall, we believe the Acquicella process can provide an important contribution to the scholarly debate on the importance of codesign in the field of building retrofitting in distressed urban areas, especially in the face of significant technological innovations. Acquicella residents' contributions to the co-design process demonstrate that inhabiting a distressed neighbourhood does not prevent people from engaging in sophisticated design conversations on structural improvements, dissipative joints, or centralized plants connected with photovoltaic panels. On the contrary, making these decisions without residents' engagement might encounter unexpected mismatches, especially in distressed areas where the concept of 'savings through technological innovations' should be framed not only in terms of single households' economics but, most importantly, in terms of relational economics (mutual accountability of centralized bills).

In broader terms, the Acquicella experience certainly supports the socio-technical scholars' argument that as technology becomes more sophisticated, co-design becomes increasingly significant and beneficial. However, since we think this plea would not necessarily impact the retrofitting game anytime soon, we think our work adds an important pragmatic dimension to the debate. It highlights an important insight for situations where engaging residents' creativity in technological and structural choices faces insurmountable obstacles. These obstacles may arise due to various constraints, such as strings attached to funding mechanisms, as in the Acquicella case, or entrenched habits and rigid mindsets among designers and developers. Our experience underscores the importance of distinguishing between two dimensions of co-design: shared creativity and negotiability. When shared creativity was constrained by circumstances, we were at least able to provide negotiable spaces.

This insight calls for more cases and research on promoting co-design in deep retrofitting processes in distressed urban areas. It suggests testing the usefulness of distinguishing between these two dimensions of co-design as a way to overcome obstacles and address controversies arising from technological decisions that directly impact residents' individual budgets and relational dynamics.

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